

Questions for excavation datasets at the A+ portal.

Working document: *Draft version 0.6 [24/11/2022]*

Suggested question format: **Q**: (*Question in simple writing*), **R**: (*Expected result*), **S**: (*Possible syntax involved*), **C**: (*Contributor/s*)

QUESTIONS

Q1

Q: *"I want to find paleolithic blades"*

R: Either the collections containing *"paleolithic blades"* or the actual items in a list.

S: E27_Site → AP21_contains → E18_Physical_Thing →

- P2_has_type → E55_Type
- P92_was_brought_into_existence → E63_Beginning_of_Existence → P10_falls_within → E4_Period
- P45_consists_of → E57_Material (possibly also needed?)

C: Markos Katsianis

Q2

Q: *"I want to find neolithic postholes"*

R: Either the collections containing *"neolithic postholes"* or the actual items in a list.

S: E27_Site → AP21_contains → E25_Human_Made_Feature/E18_Physical_Thing

- P2_has_type → E55_Type
- P92_was_brought_into_existence → E63_Beginning_of_Existence → P10_falls_within → E4_Period

C: Markos Katsianis

Q3

Q: *"I want to find excavation contexts with loamy sand texture"*

R: The excavations containing those periods or a list of contexts.

S: E27_Site → AP21_contains → A8_Stratigraphic_Unit → AP15_contains_remains_of → S10_Material_Substantial → P2_has_type → E55_Type

Or

S: E27_Site → AP21_contains → A8_Stratigraphic_Unit → P43_has_dimension → E54_Dimension → (P2_has_type → E55_Type [*loamy sand texture*] → P2_has_type → E55_Type [*texture*]) → P90_has_value → rdf:literal

C: Markos Katsianis

Q4

Q: *"I want to find gallo-roman ceramic"*

R: Either the collections containing *"gallo-roman ceramic"* or the actual items in a list.

S: E27_Site → AP21 contains → E22_Human-Made_Object

- P2_has_type → E55_Type
- P92_was_brought_into_existence → E63_Beginning_of_Existence → P10_falls_within → E4_Period

C: Florian Hivert

Q5

Q: *"I want to find objects discovered during the 1986 excavation "*

R: All the actual items found during a specific excavation at a specific time.

S: E27_Site → P8i_witnessed → S19_Encounter_Event → O19_has_found_object → E22_Human-Made_Object

- P8i_witnessed → S19_Encounter_Event → P4_has_time-span → E52_Time-Span → P82a_begin_of_the_begin → "1986-01-01T00:00:00"/P82b_end_of_the_end → "1986-12-31T23:59:58"

C: Florian Hivert

Q6

Q: *"I want to find objects discovered during the YYYY excavation "*

R: All the actual items found during a specific excavation.

S: E27_Site → P8i_witnessed → S19_Encounter_Event → O19_has_found_object → E22_Man-Made_Object

- P8i_witnessed → S19_Encounter_Event → P4_has_time-span → E52_Time-Span

C: Florian Hivert

Q7

Q: *"I want to find objects found during an excavation lead by X"*

R: All the actual items found during a specific excavation lead by a particular person

S: E27_Site → P8i_witnessed → S19_Encounter_Event → O19_has_found_object → E22_Human-Made_Object

- P8i_witnessed → S19_Encounter_Event → P14_carried_out_by → E21_Person

C: Florian Hivert

Q8

Q: *"I want to find the site located at a place"*

R: All the sites localized at the same place

S: E27_Site → P55_has_current_location → E53_Place

C: Florian Hivert

Q9

Q: *"I want to find animal bones of the genus capra in excavations dating to the Early Neolithic"*

R: All the biological object typed as animal bones which formed part of an individual from the capra genus found in excavations where the site was dated from Early Neolithic

S: E20_Biological_Object

- P2_has_type → E55_Type "Animal bones"
- P46i_forms_part_of → E20_Biological_Object → P2_has_type → E55_Type "Capra"
- O19i_was_object_found → S19_Encounter_Event → P8_took_place_on_or_within → E27_Site → P8i_witnessed → E4_Period "Early Neolithic"

C: Florian Hivert

Q10

Q: *"I want to find excavations that have recovered parts of roman roads"*

R: All the excavations where a physical object from a roman roads has been found

S: S19_Encounter_Event → O19_has_found_object → E22_Human-Made_Object → P46i_forms_part_of → E25_Human-Made_Feature → P101_had_as_general_use → E55_Type "roman roads"

C: Florian Hivert

Q11

Q: *"I want to find burials of classical period"*

R: All the burials from classical period

S: E25_Human-Made_Feature → P2_has_type → E55_Type (Burial)

- P8i_witnessed → E4_Period "Classical period"

C: Florian Hivert

Q12

Q: *"I want to find floors with mosaics"*

R: all the floors which are made of mosaics

S: E25_Human-Made_Feature → P46i_is_composed_of → E22_Man-Made_Object → P2_has_type → E55_Type "Mosaic"

- P2_has_type/P101_had_as_general_use "Floor"

C: Florian Hivert

Q13

Q: *"I want to find all stratigraphic units from site X belonging to the Early Iron Age"*

R: all the stratigraphic units from a site which was excavated and which was occupied during the Early Iron Age period

S: A2_Stratigraphic_Volume_Unit → O19i_was_object_found → S19_Encounter_Event → P8_took_place_on_or_within → E27_Site → P8i_witnessed → E4_Period "Early Iron Age"

C: Florian Hivert

Q14

Q: *"I want to find excavation pictures taken in 1964"*

R: all the documents typed as a picture created in 1964 which document an excavation

S: E31_Document → P70_documents → S19_Encounter_Event

- P94i_was_created_by → E65_Creation → P4_has_time-span → P82a_begin_of_the_begin → "1964-01-01T00:00:00"/P82b_end_of_the_end → "1964-12-31T23:59:58"

C: Florian Hivert

Q15

Q: *"I want to retrieve excavation items that have a measured value of magnetic susceptibility greater than 50"*

R: All the possible items found during an excavation where a measurement of magnetic susceptibility has been made and the result was greater than 50.

S: E1_CRM_Entity → O19i_was_object_found_by → S19_Encounter_Event

- → P39i_was_measured_by → E16_Measurement → P40_observed_dimension → E54_Dimension "> 50"
- E54_Dimension → P2_has_type → E55_Type "Magnetic susceptibility"

C: Florian Hivert

Q16

Q: *"I want to retrieve all trenches with postholes in excavation X"*

R: All the features typed as trenches which contains postholes encountered during an excavation

S: E25_Human-Made_Feature

- → p46i_forms_part_of → E27-Site "X"
- → P2_has_type "Postholes"
- → P53_has_former_or_current_location->E53_Place->P2_has_type → E55_Type "Trench"
- → O19i_was_object_found_by → S19_Encounter_Event

C: Florian Hivert & Markos Katsianis

Q17

Q: *"I want to retrieve excavations that have identified legumes seeds in their samples (flotation residue sample)"*

R: All the excavations which took samples which contained legumes seeds from their sites

S: S19_Encounter_Event → P8_took_place_on_or_within → E27_Site → O3i_was_sampled_by → S2_Sample_Taking → O5_removed → S13_Sample → P2_has_type → E55_Type "Flotation residue sample"

- S13_Sample → O10_contains → E20_Biological_Object → P2_has_type → E55_Type "Legumes seeds"

C: Florian Hivert

Q18

Q: *"I want to retrieve excavation events that happened in May 2000" or "I want to see in which locations there were active excavations in May 2000"*

R: All the excavation which took place between the 1st May 2000 and the 31 May 2000

S: S19_Encounter_Event → P4_has_time-span → E52_Time-Span → P82a_begin_of_the_begin → "2000-05-01T00:00:00"/P82b_end_of_the_end → "2000-05-31T23:59:59"

C: Florian Hivert

Q19

Q: *"I want to find excavations containing radiocarbon samples"*

R: All the excavation where a sample was taken to make radiocarbon measurement

S: S19_Encounter_Event → P8_took_place_on_or_within → E27_Site → O3i_was_sampled_by → S3_Measurement_by_Sampling → P2_has_type → E55_Type "Radiocarbon measurement"

- S3_Measurement_by_sampling → O5_removed → S13_Sample

C: Florian Hivert